

MOTIVATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING AT SANTIPHAP HIGH SCHOOL LUANGPRABANG ACADEMIC 2022-2023

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Abstract

English is a widely used language; it plays a significant part in fostering relationships and communication among speakers of many cultures and languages. The desire to learn English will also motivate students as they may prefer to travel overseas for better income, meet more people using English to comprehend their skills, or so students can meet particular educational criteria. Students won't succeed in their efforts or in their hopes of learning if they lack significant motivation. This study shows intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in English language learning perceived by students. The studies focus mainly on the high school students of Santhiphap High School in Luanprabang Lao. The researcher selected 70 participants as a sample for the study and used a questionnaire as a source for selecting the data. The researcher also used both English and Lao scripts in the questionnaire.

Keywords: Motivation, English, Learning, Lao, Language.

I. INTRODUCTION

This work introduces the background of the study, the goal of the study, the research question, the importance of the study, the scope of the study, and significant phrases. Since English is the most frequently used language, it plays a significant part in fostering relationships and communication among speakers of many cultures and languages. An important skill that secondary school children must learn in order to survive in the future's fiercely competitive world is how to communicate in English. Understanding and using English is necessary for participating in society and the country. (Mary, 1993: 21). The importance of motivation in schooling cannot be overstated. This is one of the most important topics at the same moment. How do I inspire my students? This is a question that every educator has asked themselves. In order to learn a language, one needs motivation. How to inspire students to learn a language is one of the most challenging aspects of teaching. The key is to determine the students' motivation and then make the lesson interesting and relevant to them. Motivation is a complicated human construct that is a challenging concept for people to comprehend and describe (Anjomshoa and Sadighi, 2015).

Most learners of English do so with the hope that it will be of some value to them. They desire to increase their income so they may travel overseas, meet more people, or meet more people using English, or so they can meet particular educational criteria. Students won't succeed in their efforts or in their hopes of learning if they lack significant motivation. In addition to the

function that intelligence and linguistic aptitude play in learning a second or foreign language (Gardner and Lambert, 1972 cited in Xu, 2008), motivation is an important aspect of the successful study of language acquisition. It is regarded as goal-directed and is described as "the combination of effort plus the desire to achieve the goal of learning the language plus favourable attitudes towards learning the language" (Gardner, 1985: 10). A person's desire to pursue anything is determined by their motivation. Different sorts of motivation may have varying effects on learning when it comes to learning a second language or a foreign language. Occasionally, two motivational categories are distinguished: 1) Instrumental motivation: the desire to learn a language in order to achieve certain "instrumental" objectives, such as obtaining employment, reading a foreign newspaper, or passing an exam; 2) Integrative motivation: the desire to learn a language in order to interact with speakers of that language from other cultures. (Richards et al).

The biggest public school in Viengmai Village, Luangprabang City, and Luangprabang Province is Sathiphap High School. This institution opened its doors in 1964. The Department of Education and Sports of the Province of Luangprabang oversees the teaching-learning budget in the budget for school administration. For the academic year 2022–2023, the school offers high school-level learning and instruction to first- through seventh-year students. There are 2028 students overall, 965 of them are female, and 158 teachers, 42 of whom are female. A subject that is taught from the first year to the seventh year is English Language. Teachers and students are motivated to learn and teach English for a variety of reasons, including the fact that doing so will prepare them for working with foreigners and for studying overseas.

As a result, the goal of this study is to examine how Santhiphap High School in Luangprabang City, Lunagprabang Province, motivates students to learn English. Additionally, this study sought to ascertain whether or not learning English was motivated. The study's findings may therefore have an impact on teachers and students who need to enhance their own English proficiency and the quality of English language instruction at this institution in the future.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To investigate intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in English learning perceived by students at Santiphap High School Luangprabang.
- To provide crucial knowledge and comprehension of motivation and the factors influencing students' motivation to learn English.

III. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The results of this study will show how motivated Laotian students are to learn English at Santhiphap High School in Luanprabang. The study's findings will also help Santiphap High School students learn English more effectively, provide guidelines for future motivation in English learning research, and improve English language instruction there.

IV. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study focuses on motivation in English learning at Santhiphap High School with a total of 70 participants who are students learning in grades 1 to grade 7, they were chosen to be the respondents of this study. In this study, the researcher utilizes the questionnaire to collect the data as well as the data obtained through a questionnaire with the total number of populations to define motivation in English learning.

V. METHODOLOGY

It covers the research design, study population, sample size and sampling procedure, research instruments, and an outline of the methods used to collect and analyze data, describing the procedures and strategies that were used in the implementation of the current study.

a. Research Design

This research is quantitative in nature. As a result, the researcher used a questionnaire as a method to identify the motivation for learning English in order to look at the reason for learning English at Santhiphap High School in Luangprabang. There are two questionnaires available, one in Lao and the other in English.

b. Universe And Sampling Techniques

70 pupils from grades 1 through 7 at Santhiphap High School in Luang Prabang make up the study's sample. Convenience sampling was used by the researcher to pick the sample group (Gall, Borg, & Gall, 1996).

c. Instrumentation

In order to examine motivation in English learning, this study's instrument is a questionnaire that was modified from Chawisa Pisanwacharin & Kasma Suwanarak (2020) and Huy Cuong Nguyen (2019). The questionnaire is divided into two parts: part one asks participants for information, and part two asks all 23 questions about the motivation for learning English subsequently modified questionnaires. Before using the sample group, it was examined by the adviser. The data analysis employed by the researchers was based on the mean and the S.D. of the data was also analysed. The data was calculated based on the five-point scales of LiKert (1982) as follows: (5) meaning strongly agree, (4) meaning Agree, (3) meaning Undecided, (2) meaning disagree and (1) meaning strongly disagree.

d. Data Collection Procedures

In order to gather information for our research writing, we used the following methods: First, in order to obtain the data needed to compile this final report, the researchers wrote a letter requesting authorization from the dean of the language faculty at Souphanouvong University. They then submitted it to the director of Santoph High School, asking for permission to request a financial allowance. To ensure that the pupils fully comprehend, the researcher also types the surveys in both Lao and English. In order to gather data, the researcher finally gives it to the sample group.

e. Data Analysis

After successfully gathering the necessary data, the researcher utilized the SPSS program (Statistics Package of the Social Science) to analyze the data and determine the Mean and SD (Standard Deviation) based on the five-point Likert scale that was employed in this questionnaire under the following conditions:

5	means	Strongly agree
4	means	Agree
3	means	undecided
2	means	Disagree
1	means	Strongly disagree

V. DATA ANALYSIS

a. Results of Data Types

From the results of the topic: A study of motivation in English learning at Santhiphap High School Luangprabang. According to the opinions of the participants who had answered the questionnaire forms, the analysis and the results as below.

b. Personal Information

Table I: An overview of the result of the student's gender

No	Gender	Frequency	Percentage
1	Male	35	50.00%
2	Female	35	50.00%
3	Total	70	100%

As demonstrated in Table I: The total was 70 students (100%) with the quantity of 35 male equals 50.00%, and 35 female participants conducted 50.00%.

Table II: Presents the experimental data on the result of students' age

No	Age	Frequency	Percentage
1	12-14	10	14.28 %
2	15-16	20	28.57 %
3	17-18	20	28.57 %
4	More than 18	20	28.57 %
5	Total	70	100%

With the appearance of table II: There were four age groups participated in the current study. The majority group participants age was 15-16 years old covered participants (28.57%), 17-18 years old (28.57%), 12-14 years old (14.28%) and the rest were in the age of more than 18 years old which consisted of 10 respondents equals (28.57%).

Table III: Participants' experience in English learning

No	Duration	Frequency	Percentage
1	1-2 years	20	28.57 %
2	3-4 years	20	28.57%
3	4-6 years	20	28.57 %
4	More than 6 years	10	14.28 %
5	Total	70	100%

Table III shows that participants' experience in English learning is 1-2 years equals 28.57%, 3-4 years equals 28.57%, 4-6 years equals 28.57% and more than 6 years equals 14.28 %.

c. Motivation in English Learning

Table IV: The result of students' motivation in English learning (Intrinsic Motivation)

Items	Mean	S.D
1. English is interesting and need it for learning	4.06	0.097
2. Desire to be good at English	4.52	0.116
3. Enjoy and happy while learning English	3.26	0.930
4. Be interested in the native speaker culture	4.21	0.068
5. Desire to communicate easily with native speakers	4.18	0.102
6. Desire to read English book better understand	4.09	0.133
7. Desire to travel abroad where uses English as official language	4.03	0.111
8. Be proud of developing and learning new language	3.32	0.093
9. Have a chance to meet new friends from many countries	4.03	0.111
10. Desire to use English for career in the future	4.06	0.097
11. Desire to go to study in countries where use English language	4.42	0.107
12. Further study at university with Bachelor of arts in English	3.32	0.093
Total	4.05	0.098

From table IV it shown the result of participants' intrinsic motivation in English learning are as follows: students desired to be good at English with Mean=4.52 and S.D=0.116, Students desired to go to study in countries where use English language with Mean=4.42 and S.D=0.107, Students were interested in the native speaker culture with Mean=4.21 and S.D=0.068, Students desired to communicate easily with native speakers with Mean=4.18 and S.D=0.102, Students desired to read English book better understand with Mean=4.09 and S.D=0.133, Students desired to use English for career in the future with Mean=4.06 and S.D=0.097, Students desired to travel abroad where uses English as official language, with Mean=4.03 and S.D= 0.111, Students have a chance to meet new friends from many countries with Mean=4.03 and S.D=0.111, Students were proud of developing and learning new language with Mean=3.32 and S.D=0.093, Students desired to study at university with Bachelor of arts in English with Mean=3.32 and S.D=0.093, students enjoy and happy while learning English with Mean=3.26 and S.D= 0.930. In addition, students' intrinsic motivation in English learning with total Mean= 4.05 with S.D=0.098.

Table V: The result of students' motivation in English learning (Extrinsic Motivation)

Items	Mean	S.D
1. Desire to get a higher English subject average score	4.15	0.116
2. Being proficient in English makes other people accept and respect more.	3.91	0.186
3. Be a requirement for parents	3.26	0.930
4. Desire to get a scholarship to study in domestic and abroad	4.09	0.133
5. Be not good at English as other classmate	3.79	0.129
6. Learning English is very popular	4.09	0.133
7. Expect some rewards from parents if the English test score is better.	4.27	0.146
8. Laos is a member of ASEAN so English is a requirement.	3.32	0.093
9. Gain an edge in terms of choosing a career and reaching a high income in the future	4.48	0.108
10. The careers' goal need using English	3.26	0.930
11. New technology helps people in learning English very fast and easily.	3.27	0.210
12. Be a subject in the learning program of the school	3.58	0.222
Total	3.92	0.093

From table V it shown the result of participants' Extrinsic motivation in English learning are as follows: students gain an edge in term of choosing a career and reach a high income in the future with Mean=4.48 and S.D=0.108, Students expect some rewards from parent if the English test score is better with Mean=4.27 and S.D=0.146, students desired to get higher English subjects' average score with Mean=4.15 and S.D=0.116, students desired to get scholarship to study in domestic and abroad with Mean=4.09 and S.D=0.133, students think that learning English is very popular with Mean=4.09 and S.D=0.133, students are being proficient in English makes other people accepted and respect more with Mean=3.91 and S.D=0.186, students are not good at English as others classmates with Mean=3.79 and S.D=0.129, English is a subject in learning program of school with Mean=3.58 and S.D=0.222, new technology helps people in learning English very fast and easily with Mean=3.27 and S.D=0.210, the careers' goal need using English with Mean=3.26 and S.D=0.930, be requirement from parents with Mean=3.26 and S.D=0.930. It means students' extrinsic motivation in English with a total Mean=3.92 and S. D=0.093.

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

a. The Students' Intrinsic Motivation in English Learning

The result of students' intrinsic motivation in English learning are students desired to be good at English with Mean=4.52 and S.D=0.116, Students desired to go to study in countries that use English language with Mean=4.42 and S.D=0.107, Students interested in the native speaker culture with Mean=4.21 and S.D=0.068, Students desired to communicate easily with native speakers with Mean=4.18 and S.D=0.102,

All information mentioned above is according to the theory of Ryn and Deci (2000:6) stated that intrinsic motivation is the undertaking of an activity for its inherent benefit rather than some other identifiable consequence. Intrinsic motivation exists between the individual and the activity to be performed. That is to say, not all people are motivated to do all tasks; there is a go-between that is intrinsic motivation. Because of its existence in between the individual

and task, intrinsic motivation has sometimes been defined as something being interesting or the rewards one receives from being engaged in an intrinsically motivate task intrinsic motivation is believed to result in long-term changes in behaviour and greater persistence toward achievement. An intrinsically motivated student studies because he/she wants to study.

The results are in line with past studies such as Chawisa Pisanwacharin & Kasma Suwanarak (2020) studied on the topic “A study of senior high school students’ motivation in learning English at a tutorial school”. This study aims at investigating Thai senior high school students’ intrinsic and extrinsic motivations in learning English at a tutorial school and exploring factors affecting the students’ English learning motivation. The data were collected by using a questionnaire and a semi-structured interview. The questionnaire results revealed that the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in learning English at a tutorial school was at a moderate level ($X = 2.51-3.50$). The intrinsic motivation stating that ‘Desire to be good at English’ showed the highest mean score ($X = 4.41$) while ‘Be interested in the Native Speaker culture’ showed the lowest ($X = 2.82$). The extrinsic motivation stating that ‘Gain an edge in terms of choosing a career and reach a higher income in the future’ showed the highest mean score ($X = 4.18$) while ‘Expect some rewards from parents if the English achievement test score is better showed the lowest ($X = 2.09$).

b. The Students’ Extrinsic Motivation in English Learning

The results of participants’ Extrinsic motivation in English learning are as follows: students gain an edge in terms of choosing a career and reaching a high income in the future with Mean=4.48 and S.D=0.108, Students expect some rewards from parents if the English test score is better with Mean=4.27 and S.D=0.146, students desired to get higher English subjects’ average score with Mean=4.15 and S.D=0.116.

All information mentioned above is according to the theory of Ryn and Deci (2000:6) stated that extrinsic motivation in the latter there is much more choice and autonomy than in the former. Since most of the work done in school is not intrinsically interesting to students, intrinsic motivation to engage in task students’ studies and learn for other reasons. Such a student performs in order to receive a reward, like graduating or passing a test or getting a new shirt from his or her mother, or to avoid a penalty like a failing grade, and sometimes students are motivated on their study or some activity from their parents.

The results are in line with past studies such as Huy Cuong Nguyen's (2019) study on the topic Motivation in Learning English Language: a Case Study at Vietnam National University, Hanoi. This paper focuses on investigating the type and level of motivation in English language learning. The instrument of the study was adopted from Gardner’s Attitude/Motivation Test Battery (AMTB). The participants in this study include 371 first and second-year students of Vietnam National University, Hanoi – University of Engineering and Technology (VNU-UET). The collected data were summarized and analyzed by using SPSS software. The findings show that the students that participated in the study were highly motivated in English learning, and more instrumentally motivated.

VII. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This study shows motivation in English learning at Santhiphap High School Luangprabng Province. This study found that generally, it consisted two part as personal information and motivation in English learning, the participants consisted 70 students, 35 male equals 50.00% and 35 female equals 50.00%.

The result of participants' intrinsic motivation in English learning are as follows: students desired to be good at English with Mean=4.52 and S.D=0.116, Students desired to go to study in countries where use English language with Mean=4.42 and S.D=0.107, Students were interested in the native speaker culture with Mean=4.21 and S.D=0.068, Students desired to communicate easily with native speakers with Mean=4.18 and S.D=0.102, Students desired to read English book better understand with Mean=4.09 and S.D=0.133, Students desired to use English for career in the future with Mean=4.06 and S.D=0.097, Students desired to travel abroad where uses English as official language, with Mean=4.03 and S.D= 0.111, Students have a chance to meet new friends from many countries with Mean=4.03 and S.D=0.111, Students were proud of developing and learning new language with Mean=3.32 and S.D=0.093, Students desired to study at university with Bachelor of arts in English with Mean=3.32 and S.D=0.093, students enjoy and happy while learning English with Mean=3.26 and S.D= 0.930. In addition, students' intrinsic motivation in English learning with total Mean= 4.05 with S.D=0.098.

The result of participants' Extrinsic motivation in English learning are as follows: students gain an edge in term of choosing a career and reach a high income in the future with Mean=4.48 and S.D=0.108, Students expect some rewards from parent if the English test score is better with Mean=4.27 and S.D=0.146, students desired to get higher English subjects' average score with Mean=4.15 and S.D=0.116, students desired to get scholarship to study in domestic and abroad with Mean=4.09 and S.D=0.133, students think that learning English is very popular with Mean=4.09 and S.D=0.133, students are being proficient in English makes other people accepted and respect more with Mean=3.91 and S.D=0.186, students are not good at English as others classmates with Mean=3.79 and S.D=0.129, English is a subject in learning program of school with Mean=3.58 and S.D=0.222, new technology helps people in learning English very fast and easily with Mean=3.27 and S.D=0.210, the careers' goal need using English with Mean=3.26 and S.D=0.930, be requirement from parents with Mean=3.26 and S.D=0.930. It mean students' extrinsic motivation in English with total Mean=3.92 and S.D=0.093.

In conclusion, according to the result of the research, the main finding has shown that the types of student motivation in English learning at Santhiphap High School Luangprabang province the students has motivated in English learning from both types of motivate as intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation showed that students have intrinsically motivated more than extrinsically motivated, shown in overall mean intrinsic motivation is 4.05 and extrinsic motivation 3.92. So, the researcher summarized intrinsic motivation as the dominant type of student motivation in English learning at Santhiphap High School Luangprabang.

Recommendations

This study was carried out to provide some light on the degree and kind of motivation for learning the English language among first- to seventh-year students at Santhiphap High School. The study offers important insights and information regarding motivation and the elements affecting students' motivation to learn English. By increasing the students' drive, this valuable knowledge and information will also help them become more fluent in English.

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